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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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ORTHOPEDIC CASES OF ERRORS IN PROSTHETICS ON IMPLANTS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of orthopedic dental treatment using dental implants is to create a functional and aesthetic denture, and the results can be successful only with the collective high-quality performance of the work of an orthopedic surgeon-dental technician, as well as a therapist and dental hygienist. The installed dental screw implants are functional only after the completion of the denture manufacturing stage, at various times (5-10 years) from 85 to 97%.

Keywords: orthopedic cases, implants, dental treatment, prosthetics, dental implantation.

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ИМПЛАНТЛАРДА ПРОТЕЗЛАШДА ОРТОПЕДИК ХОЛАТЛАРДАГИ ХАТОЛИКЛАР

ANNOTATSIYA

Tish implantlari yordamida ortopedik stomatologik davolashning maqsadi -funksional va estetik talablarga to'liq javob beradigan protezni yaratishdir va bunaqa natijalarga erishish uchun faqatgina ortoped-jarroh-stomatolog, shuningdek terapevt va stomatologning jamoaviy yuqori sifatli ishlashi bilan muvaffaqiyatli bo'lishi mumkin. O'rnatilgan tish implantlari faqat protez ishlab chiqarish bosqichi tugagandan so'ng, turli vaqtlarda (5-10 yil) 85 dan 97% gacha funksional holati yaxshi saqlanishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: ortopedik holatlar, implantlar, tishlarni davolash, protezlash, tish implantatsiyasi.

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ОРТОПЕДИЧЕСКИЕ СЛУЧАИ ОШИБОК ПРИ ПРОТЕЗИРОВАНИИ НА ИМПЛАНТАТАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Целью ортопедического лечения зубов с использованием зубных имплантатов является создание функционального и эстетичного зубного протеза, и результаты могут быть успешными только при совместном качественном выполнении работы хирурга-ортопеда-зубного техника, а также терапевта и стоматолога-гигиениста. Установленные зубные винтовые имплантаты работоспособны только после завершения этапа изготовления зубного протеза, в разное время (5-10 лет) от 85 до 97%.

Ключевые слова: ортопедические случаи, имплантаты, лечение зубов, протезирование, дентальная имплантация.

Relevance

Prosthetics on implants is the most popular way to restore chewing and aesthetic function in patients with adentia. Missing teeth can be replaced with either non-removable or removable dentures supported by implants [1,2]. The clinical decision to choose between these two different methods of dental restoration is based on anatomical, aesthetic and economic factors, and most importantly – on the wishes of the patient. High survival and low incidence of complications in prosthetics on implants are important conditions for the overall success of treatment, since failures in prosthetics can lead to the failure of the entire implantation rehabilitation [4]. One of the most important strategies for reducing the risk of errors is a comprehensive preliminary diagnostic examination, after which a decision is made on the manufacture of a non-removable or removable prosthesis on implants. In accordance with the prosthetics plan, the number of implants should be determined, as well as their ideal three-dimensional position in mesio-distal, bucco-oral and vertical dimensions [6].

5 mistakes during dental implantation

- Poor planning and lack of quality diagnostics ...
- Choosing the wrong implant ...
- Incorrect actions of the doctor during implantation ...
- Wrong choice of prosthetics method ...
- Insufficient care in the postoperative period

1. POOR PLANNING AND LACK OF QUALITY DIAGNOSTICS

Inappropriate planning of the implantation operation may lead to the implant being placed in the wrong position (for example, too much tilt, placing the implants past the bone, too close to each other or to the natural roots of the teeth) or the discovery of a lack of bone tissue to support it [7]. This can lead to unsuccessful implantation of the implant or damage to important structures — nerves, blood vessels and adjacent teeth. It is also important to note the problem of incorrect choice of anesthetics for a particular patient. This can happen if, before using them, the surgeon has not made sure that the patient has no specific reactions to the proposed anesthetic, as well as no additional diagnoses, chronic diseases and other factors that may affect susceptibility to certain painkillers [8].

2. CHOOSING THE WRONG IMPLANT

Not all implants may be suitable for patients. For this reason, they must be carefully selected by a specialist. The choice itself depends on various factors, such as the degree of tooth loss, the location of the implant, as well as the condition and volume of available bone tissue. Therefore, at the stage of implant selection, it is necessary to take into account the individual anatomical characteristics of each patient. Incorrect implant selection can lead to complications during and after the procedure [8].

3. INCORRECT ACTIONS OF THE DOCTOR DURING IMPLANTATION

Errors that may occur in the dental implantologist during surgery include penetration of boron into the nasal cavity, complete or partial absence of primary fixation, the occurrence of bone burns during cutting and calibration of the implant bed [9].

4. WRONG CHOICE OF PROSTHETICS METHOD

This can have far-reaching consequences for the patient. Along with bite problems, jaw pain and other troubles, an incorrectly selected prosthesis can lead to complications. These include, for

example, speech disorders, loss of chewing function, inflammation and irritation of the mucous membrane, and psychological discomfort.

5. INSUFFICIENT CARE IN THE POSTOPERATIVE PERIOD

Improper care of the implant after surgery can lead to an accumulation of bacteria, especially in the gum area. This, in turn, will cause mucositis, a pathological inflammatory and destructive process that, if not treated in a timely manner, can lead to the destruction of the connection between the implant and surrounding tissues. At the stage of mucositis, an artificial root can be saved. However, if it turns into peri-implantitis, when inflammation affects bone tissue and causes its destruction, you will have to consider removing the implant [8].

Medical errors when installing dental implants

Dental implantation, although small, is still a serious surgical operation that requires a qualified approach, medical experience and the use of modern technologies. In many clinics (including VivaDent dentistry), the risks of errors during implantation are minimized, but they cannot be completely excluded, and even more so you should know.

What errors occur during implantation and prosthetics on an implant?

All possible errors during surgical intervention can be divided into two groups: without using scientific medical terminology, they can be called errors of the surgeon and errors of the orthodontist.

Mistakes of the surgeon

Errors of a purely surgical nature include such incorrect actions:

- disregard for the rules of antiseptics and asepsis (i.e. work in non-sterile conditions, unclean tools, etc.);
- incorrect selection of anesthetics for a particular patient (after all, before administering anesthesia, the operating surgeon must find out whether this person has specific reactions to the proposed anesthetic, whether there are additional diagnoses, chronic diseases, etc., which may affect susceptibility to certain painkillers);
- incorrect administration of an anesthetic (at the wrong point, in the wrong volume, etc.);
- inattention to the presence of anatomical features in the operated area of the patient;
- carelessness when handling alveolar ridge tissues;
- incorrect selection of the diameter of the dental implant — if it exceeds the diameter of the mucotome;
- the drills do not cool down while working with them, their speed is selected incorrectly;
- the selection and use of drills is not in the same sequence (according to the rules, it should be selected from a smaller diameter to a larger one — although this is not always relevant);
- the distance between the implants and the roots of adjacent teeth is not observed;
- the dental implant is inserted into the prepared well at the wrong speed (it cannot be inserted quickly and simply, like a designer part, — the doctor must monitor the insertion all the time so as not to damage the tissue and cause complications during healing);
- the whole operation is carried out too hastily or too slowly (both have their negative sides and their risks) [9].

Orthodontist's mistakes

Basically, these are the inaccuracies that ultimately make the implant not ideally suited for installation to a particular patient, as well as errors in the installation of the implant. The orthodontist's mistakes when installing dental implants include:

- the supporting parts are not accurately prepared;
- the axes of the supporting elements of the implant are not parallel;
- fewer supports than necessary;
- the height of the lower facial region is incorrectly determined;
- the neck of the implant does not fit tightly with the edges of the crown — that is, these elements are poorly fitted;
- the length of the implant and the height of the tooth crown are correlated in the wrong proportion;
- the width of the crown is significantly larger than the diameter of the implant;
- the crown attached to the implant contains a part of an artificial gum made of plastic;
- the axis of the crown and the axis of the dental implant have an angle between them exceeding 27 degrees;
- the configuration of the tooth crown is incorrect, which is why there is a risk of unwinding or breaking the abutment;
- the gap between the abutment and the implant itself, which leads to poor fixation;
- the prosthesis on the dental implant is poorly fixed, which may cause cementation or the screw fixing the crown may be unscrewed;
- the fissure-tubercle contacts, which should be between the implanted artificial tooth and the "native" antagonist teeth, are formed incorrectly, which can eventually lead to traumatic occlusion;
- the garland of the implant crown is poorly polished, has an insufficiently smooth surface;
- the denture is fixed in a rigid way on the implant and conditionally "movable" teeth;
- the inter-coronal spaces are too narrow, which will make it difficult for the patient to clean them and perform hygienic procedures;
- gingival risk factors and periodontitis risks are not taken into account;
- the dimensions of the console and the crown are not correlated (i.e. the implant will be permanently overloaded on one side) [6].

How can the risk be reduced?

In order to significantly reduce the risk of errors in dental implantation and prosthetics, in such modern clinics, to which VivaDent unconditionally belongs, a tomographic examination of the operated area of the patient is first performed. After that, in special computer programs, a three-dimensional model (the so-called "implantological template model") is created, which shows in great detail how the implant will be installed. Focusing on this model, implants themselves are made for a specific patient and then surgical intervention is performed[8].

Goal

In recent years, many systematic reviews have been conducted to assess the survival and complication rate of fixed and removable dentures on implants. This review examines the most common complications of prosthetics for both fixed and removable dentures on implants, including risk factors for their development, prerequisites for early and late implant survival, as well as prevention and treatment of complications.

Results.

This review of the literature on fixed and removable implant-supported prostheses shows that technical complications cannot be avoided with any type of implant-supported prostheses. Technical complications can lead to failure of treatment on implants. To reduce the risk of such failure, a comprehensive preliminary diagnostic examination is crucial, including determining the purpose of prosthetics using a wax model or kit and the corresponding ideal, prosthesis-oriented three-dimensional position of the implant. In addition, choosing the ideal type of prosthesis, including the appropriate components and implant materials, is important for the clinical success of reconstruction in the long term.

CONCLUSIONS. This review of the literature on fixed and removable implant-retained prostheses demonstrates that technical complications cannot be avoided in either type of implant-retained prosthesis. Technical complications can lead to the failure of implant treatment. To reduce the risk of this failure, a comprehensive pretreatment diagnostic work-up, including defining the prosthetic goal with the aid of a wax-up or set-up and the associated ideal, prosthetic-oriented three-dimensional implant position, is crucial. Furthermore, selection of the ideal type of prosthesis, including the respective implant components and materials, is important for the clinical long-term success of the reconstruction.

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